

University of
Zurich^{UZH}

Institute of Asian and Oriental Studies – Chinese Studies
University Research Priority Program (URPP) Asia and Europe

The *Gongsunlongzi* and Other Neglected Texts

Aligning Philosophical and Philological Perspectives

Conference, Zurich, August 27–29, 2014

Conference Outline

The Gongsunlongzi is one of the few early Chinese received texts dealing with problems of logic and epistemology. Unfortunately, philological inquiries suggest that most probably huge parts were only composed during the Chinese Medieval period (3rd–7th centuries AD). Philosophical studies on the text usually take its authenticity for granted and consider the Gongsunlongzi as if it actually were a Warring States text (453–221 BC). Philological evidence speaking against this widely shared assumption tends to be ignored. Yet, the materials included in the received text are rather heterogeneous and any information about the context or reading instructions are lacking. As a consequence, any interpretation heavily relies on the premises of the reader. A more accurate philological study might not only provide a clearer picture of the process of composition of the Gongsunlongzi and the dating of the different textual layers that compose the text, but might also provide useful information about the context and valuable clues for its interpretation. The workshop aims at bringing together several scholars both in philosophical and philological studies, sharing an interest in the Gongsunlongzi. By contributing their complementary expertise, it is hoped that the workshop will provide ideal conditions for developing a more comprehensive perspective on the text, yielding new insights on the Gongsunlongzi and shedding light on the modalities in which questions of logic and epistemology were addressed in early and medieval China.

Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Behr, Dr. Lisa Indraccolo, Dr. Rafael Suter

Program

Wednesday, August 27, 2014

Museum Rietberg, Park-Villa Rieter, Lecture Hall, Seestrasse 110, 8002 Zurich

18:30 **Welcome and opening speech**
Rafael Suter / Lisa Indraccolo / Wolfgang Behr, University of Zurich

Thursday, August 28, 2014

KO2 F-174, University of Zurich, Main Building, Karl Schmid-Strasse 4, 8006 Zurich

9:00 **Session 1**

Bo Mou (San José State University)

An Examination of Gongsun Long's Double-Reference Thought: Engaging Fregean and Kripkean Approaches to How Reference is Possible

Fung Yiu-ming 馮耀明 (Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

Reference and Ontology in the Gongsun Longzi

10:30 **Coffee Break**

10:45 **Session 2**

Thierry Lucas (Université Catholique de Louvain [Louvain-la-Neuve], Belgium)

Logically significant words in the Gongsunlongzi

Rafał Jan Felbur (Stanford University)

The Logic of Identity in Sengzhao

12:30 Lunch Break

14:00 Session 3

Dennis Schilling (University of Munich/National Chengchi University Taipei)

Place as a category in the 'Treatise on Names and Reality' (名實論)

Liu Tisheng (Canton Huanan Normal University)

公孙龙《指物论》篇悬解 (Preliminary Title)

15:30 Coffee Break

15:45 Session 4

Ernst-Joachim Vierheller (University of Hamburg)

On Classifying (Declassifying) Things 指〔齊〕物論: Reading the Gongsun Longzi in the light of the Zhuangzi

Zhou Changzhong (Shanghai Academy of Social Sciences)

“白马论”: 实质的语言分析哲学思想 — 兼论今本《公孙龙子》作为残真本

18:00–19:00 Roundtable discussion

Friday, August 29, 2014

KO2 F-174, University of Zurich, Main Building, Karl Schmid-Strasse 4, 8006 Zurich

9:00

Session 5

Ian Johnston

The Relationship of the Gongsun Longzi to the Dialectical Chapters of the Mozi

Wang Ping (The University of New South Wales, Australia)

Interpretations of the Gongsun Longzi – A Historical Overview

10:30

Coffee Break

10:45

Session 6

Jiang Xiangdong (Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, Beijing)

《公孫龍子·白馬論》新註

Lukáš Zádrapa (Charles University, Prague)

Linguistic Affinities of the Yinwenzi Text in the Light of Basic Corpus Data

12:15–13:00

Roundtable discussion

General Information

Locations	<i>August 27</i> Museum Rietberg Park-Villa Rieter Lecture Hall Seestrasse 110 CH-8002 Zurich	<i>August 28–29</i> University of Zurich Main Building Room KO2 F-174 Karl Schmid-Strasse 4 CH-8006 Zurich
Convenors	Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Behr, Dr. Lisa Indraccolo, Dr. Rafael Suter	
Organization	Institute of Asian and Oriental Studies – Chinese Studies University Research Priority Program (URPP) Asia and Europe	
Registration	Registration required: lisa.indraccolo@uzh.ch	
Internet	www.asienundeuropa.uzh.ch/events/conferences/gongsunlongzi.html	

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